

Search for New Oral Hypoglycemic Agents. Part IV. Synthesis of Some New Substituted Biurets

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Several substituted biurets have been prepared for evaluation of their hypoglycemic activity.

As urea or thiourea moiety comprises part of the structure of oral antidiabetic agents¹ and furan derivatives have also been reported to possess hypoglycemic²⁻⁴ activity, several 1,5-diphenyl(substituted)-1-furfuryl biurets (I), 1,5-diphenyl(substituted)-1-furfuryl 2,4-dithiobiurets (II), 1,5-diphenyl(substituted)-1-furfuryl 2-thiobiurets (III), and 1,5-diphenyl(substituted)-1-furfuryl 4-thiobiurets(IV) have been synthesised for evaluation of their hypoglycemic activity.

In the present investigation, *para*-substituted monoaryl-ureas and -thioureas were condensed with furfuryl chloride to furnish furfuryl-ureas and -thioureas. These were in turn condensed with phenyl isocyanate and isothiocyanate separately. The melting point, yield, analysis, etc. of the compounds are recorded in the tables.

EXPERIMENTAL

Monoaryl-ureas and -thioureas were prepared according to Tiwari and Swaroop⁷. Furfuryl chloride was prepared by modifying the method of Sherman and Amstutz⁷. To a mixture of 2-furfuryl alcohol (0.2*M*), anhydrous pyridine (0.2*M*), and absolute ether

1. Tiwari and Swaroop, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 394.
2. Nath and Sahu, *Science*, 1954, 119, 349.
3. *Idem*, *Metabolism Clin. & Exptl.*, 1956, 5, 8.
4. Nath and Bakshi, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1959, 73, 65.
5. Danowski and Matteer, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, 74, Art 3, 971-8.
6. Haak, *Azeimittle Forsch.*, 1958, 8, 444.
7. Sherman and Amstutz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3195.

(25 ml), cooled to 5°, a solution of purified thionyl chloride (0.2M) in hexane (15 ml) was rapidly added, maintaining the temperature below 20°. The mixture was stirred for 20 minutes, extracted with dry ether (×3) and finally washed with a 50% KOH solution. The ethereal extract was dried (Na₂SO₄), the ether removed, and distilled when a colorless liquid was obtained.

Furfuryl-urea and -thiourea.—The ethereal solution of furfuryl chloride (0.05M) was added to an ethereal solution of the appropriate dried arylurea or arylthiourea (0.05M) and kept over crushed KOH (15 g.). The mixture was continuously stirred from 1 to 2 hours, kept overnight at room temperature, and then filtered. The ether was removed from the filtrate. The residual furfuryl-ureas or -thioureas were recrystallised from chloroform. Those ureas and thioureas were characterised by preparing their hydrochlorides and picrates (Tables IA and IB).

TABLE IA

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1. Furfurylureas.					
H	246°	68%	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	12.80	12.96
Me	208°	64	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	12.09	12.18
OMe	200°	62	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂	11.20	11.40
Cl	218°	64	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	11.10	11.20
2. Picrates.					
H	Explodes at high temp.	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₉ N ₅	15.68	15.74
Me	"	72	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₉ N ₅	15.17	15.24
OMe	"	74	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₁₀ N ₅	14.60	14.74
Cl	"	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₉ N ₅ Cl	14.50	14.61
3. Hydrochlorides.					
H	Does not melt	90	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	11.00	11.11
Me	"	90	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	10.20	10.63
OMe	Decomp. at high temp.	86	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl	9.70	9.93
Cl	Does not melt	91	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	9.30	9.79

TABLE IB

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
1. Furfuryl thioureas.					
H	252°	64%	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	11.90	12.07
Me	210°	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	11.30	11.40
OMe	216°	63	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	10.60	10.69
Cl	222°	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ON ₂ ClS	10.48	10.53
2. Picrates.					
H	Explodes at high temp.	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₈ N ₂ S	15.00	15.18
Me	"	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₈ N ₂ S	14.60	14.74
OMe	"	70	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₉ N ₂ S	14.10	14.26
Cl	"	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₈ N ₂ ClS	14.60	14.14
3. Hydrochlorides.					
H	Explodes at high temp.	98	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON ₂ ClS	10.80	10.45
Me	"	90	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ON ₂ ClS	9.70	9.25
OMe	"	92	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	9.30	9.24
Cl	"	94	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ ON ₂ Cl ₂ S	9.10	9.37

Furfuryl-thiobiurets and -4-thiobiurets.—A mixture of phenyl isothiocyanate (0.05M) and the appropriate furfuryl-urea or -thiourea (0.05M) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 10 hours. The mixture was concentrated and dried over calcium chloride for 2 days. The substituted thiobiurets, which crystallised, were collected and recrystallised from ethanol (Tables IIA and IIB).

TABLE II A
(Vide structure IV)

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
H	71°	64%	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	11.70	11.98
Me	122°	62	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	11.43	11.50
OMe	58°	58	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	10.98	11.02
Cl	74°	50	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	10.76	10.91

TABLE II B
(Vide structure II)

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
H	63°	64%	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ ON ₃ S ₂	11.13	11.44
Me	128°	58	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ ON ₃ S ₂	10.62	10.74
OMe	98°	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂	10.27	10.53
Cl	79°	56	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ ON ₃ ClS ₂	10.34	10.48

Furfuryl-biurets and -2-thiobiurets.—A mixture of phenyl isocyanate (0.05M) and the appropriate furfuryl-urea or -thiourea (0.05M) in dry benzene was refluxed for 45 minutes under anhydrous condition. The crystals of thiobiurets were collected and recrystallised from hot ethanol (Tables IIIA and IIIB).

TABLE III A
(Vide structure I)

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
H	174°	56%	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃	12.30	12.54
Me	213°	58	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	11.90	12.03
OMe	300°	52	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₃	11.20	11.50
Cl	300°	80	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.10	11.38

TABLE III B

(Vide structure III)

R.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Reqd.
H	218°	70%	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₃ S	11.80	11.96
Me	> 300°	72	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃ S	11.30	11.50
OMe	219°	68	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	10.90	11.02
Cl	214°	78	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ ClS	10.30	10.91

The m. p., yields, and analysis etc. of the biurets and thiobiurets are listed in the tables.

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